

Measuring Urban Heat Island Intensity in London During the Warmest June on Record

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Summary

Understanding and managing urban heat is important for climate mitigation planning, requiring spatially and temporally detailed air temperature data. This study applies a distributed network of 25 bespoke LoRaWAN air temperature sensors to examine Urban Heat Island Intensity (UHII) across London during June 2025, the warmest June on record. Results show a maximum UHII of 2.8°C, with significant intensification during two major heatwaves, and stronger nocturnal intensity. The findings also demonstrated the efficacy of low-cost, distributed sensing for monitoring extreme urban heat and informing local climate resilience strategies.

KEYWORDS: [Urban Heat Islands, London, Climate Mitigation Planning, Internet of Things, LoRaWAN Sensors]

1. Introduction

June 2025 was the warmest June for England on record, featuring two heatwaves between 16–21 June and 27–30 June according to the Met Office (Met Office, 2025). Within dense urban environments like London, these extreme events are further intensified by the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect, whereby urban areas exhibit higher temperatures than their rural surroundings (Oke *et al.*, 2017). When elevated urban baseline temperatures coincide with heatwaves, the duration and intensity of heat exposure can be further amplified as heatwaves exacerbate existing UHI conditions, and their synergistic interaction significantly increases urban vulnerability to heat stress (Cheval *et al.*, 2024).

Mitigating UHI effects and heatwaves to reduce climate-related mortality and enhance urban resilience is a global priority aligned with United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3 and 11 (United Nation, 2015). Locally, the London Plan mandates reducing extreme temperatures through a "Cooling Hierarchy," yet the policy lacks a detailed spatial methodology to monitor thermal patterns across the city's complex morphology (Mayor of London, 2021). Existing official meteorological stations are often spatially sparse while crowdsourced data remains unevenly distributed across England and Wales and can be of varying quality, hindering the ability to capture localised thermal variations (Brousse *et al.*, 2024). Studies have already shown that low-cost sensors can be used for studying the urban air temperatures and related heat stress in different urban areas (Van de Walle *et al.*, 2022; Ma

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et al., 2024, 2025a) and further encourage sensor networks to address research and local knowledge gaps induced by current data gaps (Brousse *et al.*, 2025). Thus, this paper utilises a bespoke Internet of Things (IoT) air temperature sensor network using Long Range Wide Area Network (LoRaWAN) communication to observe Urban Heat Island Intensity (UHII) across 25 locations in Greater London. The study assesses spatial gradients, diurnal behaviour, and heatwave-related amplification during an unprecedented extreme heat period.

2. Methodology

The sensing infrastructure and hardware validation used in this study follow the protocols documented previously, where co-located testing against a semi-professional Davis weather station showed that 97.5% of observations fell within ± 0.5 °C prior to data filtering, and a post-cleaning inter-sensor standard deviation of 0.20 °C was observed following 1.5×IQR data cleansing (Ma *et al.*, 2025b). The sensors were deployed following a consistent, researcher-led installation strategy at 2-3 meters high, measuring and transmitting air temperature at five-minute intervals, forming a distributed observation network that captures both spatial and temporal variations in urban thermal environments. This study integrates June 2025 temperature data from previous case studies (the one remaining active sensor from a schools project conducted in association with the Greater London Authority (GLA) and a land cover temperature study of the Queen Elizabeth Olympic Park conducted with the London Legacy Development Corporation (LLDC), see Ma *et al.*, 2025a & b) with recent Citizen Science deployments, forming a network, albeit unevenly distributed, of twenty-five bespoke sensors across London. Figure 1 shows their spatial distribution, with distances to the London centre (traditionally defined as Charing Cross) ranging from 2 km to 17.81 km.

Figure 1 Spatial Distribution of the 25 Sensors across Greater London

Data collected at a single sensor location is likely to be affected by localised microclimate conditions and introduce site-specific measurement noise. Thus, a k-means clustering approach is used to group sensor locations into clusters (Figure 2) according to their distance from Charing Cross to examine UHI intensity in greater detail, while enhancing the representativeness and stability of the temperature measurements within each analytical zone. The optimal cluster count was validated through a sensitivity analysis (k=2 to 6) using the Silhouette method.

Three categories were defined:

1. Most Central Pair (MCP): (CS11, StVincent School).
2. Other London Stations (OLS): The remaining 22 sensors.
3. Reference Point (RP): (CS1), located in Essex, outside the London municipal boundary, used as the baseline T_{RP}

The calculated UHII (UHI Intensity) was defined as:

$$UHII = T_{\text{Sensor}} - T_{RP}$$

Figure 2 Sensor Grouping by Distance Using K-Means Clustering (k = 3)

3. Results

Figure 3 presents the measured temperature from the twenty-five sensor locations against their distance from Central London. Stations located closer to the city centre generally recorded higher temperatures than those further away, with the most distant station (just outside the Greater London boundary in Essex) showing the lowest values. The cluster of sensors within the Olympic Park (points with similar distances on the plot) recorded slightly lower temperatures, suggesting a potential cooling effect from the park’s vegetation and water body – as reported by Brousse et al. (2025). Figure 4 shows diurnal temperature cycles and observed ranges by cluster, indicating a steady nocturnal UHII of 1.5°C (MCP) and 0.7°C (OLS). Daytime fluctuations are driven by a combination of UHI, local microclimate (Sky View Factor, building density, and green fraction), and localised shading, along with related Stevenson screen deficiencies, causing measurement error as reported in (Ma *et al.*, 2025b).

Figure 3 Relationship between Monthly Maximum, Minimum, and Mean Temperature and Distance from Charing Cross

Figure 4 Diurnal Temperature Cycle and Observed Ranges across Spatial Clusters (June 2025)

Figure 5 displays the time series of the three clusters across the month (top panel) and their temperature differences relative to the Essex reference site (bottom panel). Both clusters located within London consistently recorded higher temperatures than the Essex reference. The observed UHII during June 2025 ranged from 0.4°C to 2.8°C. Peaks in UHII corresponded to the two heatwave periods (16–21 June and 27–30 June). Figure 6 isolates these events, indicating stronger UHII during both heatwaves, particularly during the first, and consistently higher temperatures in the central cluster.

Figure 5 Diurnal Temperature Variation and Computed UHI Intensity across Sensor Clusters

Figure 6 Comparison of Heatwave and Non-Heatwave UHI Intensity (June 2025)

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This study reported UHII from 25 locations during England's warmest June on record. Temperatures were higher closer to the city centre, with the Olympic Park forming a slightly cooler cluster consistent with a park-cooling effect, agreeing with the moderating influence of large urban green spaces reported in previous London-based studies (Brousse et al., 2025). K-means clustering into central, intermediate and reference groups produced UHII ranging from 0.4 °C to 2.8 °C, with stronger UHI effects during the two heatwave periods. These findings align with established evidence that UHI intensify during extreme heat events and are typically strongest at night (Oke et al., 2017; Cheval et al., 2024). Our bespoke LoRaWAN sensor network was able to resolve the UHI at the city scale, while acknowledging that interpretation is constrained by limited and uneven sensor distribution. Thus, this scalable sensing system offers a viable solution to support the London Plan in monitoring and mitigating urban heat risks.

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Biographies

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Oscar Brousse is a lecturer at Bartlett Institute of Environmental Design and Engineering, University College London. He was trained as a geographer specialized in urban climate studies and modelling. His work relates urban climates to climatic health hazards such as heat-strokes, thermal discomfort or local surges of vector borne diseases.